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WP1- Deliverable D 1.1 : Contacted graphene nanoribbon

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Summary. Graphene nanoribbons (GNRs) grown epitaxially on silicon carbide (SiC) substrates could serve as key building block for future graphene-based nanoelectronic devices, and as platform to study quantum transport at the nanoscale. The deterministic and ordered growth of graphene on the silicon terminated face of SiC enables, in principle, the bottom-up growth of either zig-zag (ZZ) or armchair (AC) terminated GNRs (Fig.1). Baringhaus et al. showed that bottom-up grown GNRs are disorder-free and can support ballistic transport of carriers for distances of up to 16 μm [1]. Such transport results have not been reproduced by other groups [1-3]. In this deliverable we report microfabrication and graphene growth processes to produce epitaxial GNRs on SiC. Moreover, we report our first results of electron transport obtained by contacting epitaxial GNRs. The ability to produce epitaxial GNRs lay the foundations for deliverable D1.3 (year 3), aiming at performing scanning tunneling spectroscopy of GNRs.

Figure 1. Epitaxy of graphene on the silicon terminated face of SiC [0001]. The graphene lattice grows rotated 30 deg respect to the SiC lattice. The zigzag (ZZ) terminated edges of graphene are found along the SiC planes oriented in the $\langle 11-20 \rangle$ direction; the armchair (AC) edges of graphene run along the $\langle 1-100 \rangle$ directions in SiC.

Epitaxial growth of GNRs. Bottom-up growth of GNRs requires the controlled growth of the 0-layer (also known as buffer layer) on the surface of SiC (Fig.1). The 0-layer grown on the Si-face [0001] is a highly ordered 2D material, but it is electrically insulating due to the presence of covalent bonds to the SiC substrate. However, the 0-layer is decoupled from the substrate on certain facets of the SiC surface, e.g. the $\langle 11-2n \rangle$ directions in Fig.1, leading to quasi-free standing graphene on the substrate step edges. While epitaxial growth of monolayer graphene over SiC is a well-established technology [4,5], growth of the 0-layer over large area is not. Our route to produce epitaxial GNRs on SiC involves a) the patterning of the SiC substrate and b) subsequent growth of 0-layer on the surface. Figure 2a-e shows the microfabrication steps involved to pattern 5 to 100 nm steps on SiC by a combination of electron-beam lithography and reactive-ion etching (RIE). Figure 2f shows a micrograph of the different geometries patterned on SiC before 0-layer growth.

Figure 2: Patterning of SiC prior growth GNRs. The Fabrication process developed in this project includes: (a) direct laser writer (DLW) was used to pattern SiC (0001) surface, which uses single source laser with the wavelength 405nm and the spot size of 100nm. Since, SiC is transparent, a two layer resist process is used to overcome the focusing issue. (b) MF319 is used to develop the exposed part of the resist S1805. (c) pattern is transferred to LOR3A by a subsequent O₂ plasma treatment. (d) This pattern is transferred on to the SiC substrate by a reactive ion etching process (RIE). In the RIE process we used NF₃/O₂ plasma, giving controllable SiC etch rates down to 0.7nm/sec. (e) After the etching process, remover 1165 is used to strip the residues of the resist from the surface of SiC substrate. (f) Micrograph of some of the geometries patterned on SiC.

(a) Laser writer (b) Dev- MF319 (c) Ashing O₂ plasma (d) RIE of SiC (e) Remover 1165 (f) Micrograph of some of the geometries patterned on SiC.

After introducing step-edges on the surface of SiC, the growth of GNRs proceeds in two steps, a) the substrates undergo a thermal process at 1300°C for 3 hours to reconstruct the surface (e.g. step-edges sidewalls) and b)

GNR growth at 1800°C for 1 min in 800 mbar argon atmosphere. Figure 3 shows surface analysis after GNR growth, including a confirmation of crystallinity of the 0-layer growth in this method at synchrotron facility.

Figure 3: Surface characterization of GNRs. (a) Low energy electron microscopy (LEEM) performed at synchrotron facility (MAX IV, Lund). (b) low energy electron diffraction (LEED) pattern of the 0-layer area (e.g. yellow circle in (a)) confirms the long-range order of the buffer grown over SiC (0001) surface. (c) AFM line profile of the etched trenches, on an area similar to the dashed line in (a) shows that the step height is about 10-15 nm.

Electrical contacts to GNR. We have found that palladium provides a reliable contact material to epitaxial GNRs (Figure 4a). Contacts are deposited in two e-beam step: i) Large Au bonding pads (5 nm Ti sticking layer), overlapping ii) fine Pd contacts to GNRs. For the large Au contact deposition, the buffer layer has to be etched by oxygen plasma, so that a better adhesion between Ti/Au metal and SiC substrate is achieved. Figure 4b shows an example of (two-terminal) temperature dependence of GNRs resistance. Figure 4c shows the two point magnetoresistance measurements ($T=4$ K) in the range -10 T to 10 T, showing a five-fold drop in resistance respect to $B = 0$ T (manuscript under preparation).

Figure 1: Contacted epitaxial GNR. (a) AFM scan showing Pd contacts represented in black and GNR indicated by the black dotted line. (b) Temperature dependence of the GNR resistance (2-terminal) measurements. (c) Five-fold drop in GNR resistance from $B=0$ to $B=5$ T ($T=4$ K)

Outlook. Quantum transport on GNRs requires the ability to tune the carrier density (Fermi level) by e.g. electrostatic gate. Having developed a process to produce epitaxial GNRs, to this end, we are developing gated GNRs using hexagonal boron nitride as gate dielectric (Figure 5). Electron transport will be explored in such gated GNRs devices and compared with the outcome of D1.3, STS spectroscopy of GNRs.

References

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Figure 5: Towards gated GNRs devices using hexagonal boron nitride as gate dielectric, dry-transferred onto the GNR.